

Subjugation and Suppression of Women in Khaled Hosseini's *A Thousand Splendid Suns*

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R.S.Namirah

I M.A. in English Literature
Govindammal Aditanar College for Women
Tiruchendur

Abstract

Khaled Hosseini, in his novel, A Thousand Splendid Suns has depicted the pathetic condition of women. It is being suppressed by abusive men who torture them in daily life. It describes the problems and cruelty faced by Nana, Marian and Laila, Afghani Women who were under the Taliban rule in Afghanistan. Society always keeps shaping women to be subordinate, submissive and to obey the men as a slave. This Novel shows the deep feeling of women's tear, and their struggle from layer to layer. It is written in the third person's point of view. In this novel, Khaled Hosseini reveals the real face of an abusive husband and the look of society.

Keywords: *Illegitimate, Polygamy, Marginalization, Suppressed, Subjugation.*

In 1965 Khaled Hosseini was born in Kabul where his father was a diplomat, and his mother taught Farsi and history. After the 1978 coup and the ensuing Russian invasion, the family fled from Afghanistan for the United States, receiving political asylum in 1980. They settled in SanJose, California where his father found work as a driving professor. Hosseini is a doctor and lives with his wife and two children in Northern California. *The Kite Runner*, his first novel, has been met with great critical and widespread acclaim.

A Thousand Splendid Suns follow the novel the struggle of two women characters, Mariam and Laila due to the torture and violent behaviour of their cruel husband. They suffer through hardship, and they are treated very severely, both physically and mentally. Their Continuous affliction leads hope to fade away. Anxiety, stress and fear make Mariam and Laila move away from the country.

Nana was raped by Jalil her servant and Mariam was born as an illegitimate daughter. She was called Harami, which means unwanted thing. In the society of Afghan, Women are not allowed to go out to learn. So Mariam learns at home with the help of Mullah Faizullah, and she learns to read and write Koran. She requests her mother to allow her to go to school, but her mother asked her to endure life. "What's the sense of schooling a girl like you? And you'll learn nothing of value in those schools" (18). Being an illegitimate daughter, she longs for love, kindness, the family house and the acceptance of society. Which all other legitimate claim and she was

cornered and marginalised for the status of being Harami. “A man’s heart is a wretched thing, Mariam. It isn’t like a mother’s womb. It won’t bleed; it won’t stretch to make room for you. I am the only one who loves you. I’m all you have in this world, Mariam and when I’m gone, you’ll have nothing. You’ll have nothing. You are nothing!”(27).

In the Patriarchal society, all men, including Rasheed and Jalil, give importance to their reputation. They can move to any extreme to protect their fake name as the right person. Nana becomes pregnant. Jalil is much afraid of society. He makes Nana and her child move away from Herat and causes them to stay in the small hut which is called rat hole by “And so, Your father built us this rathole”(Pg: 8). Nana, while all other wives of Jalil are living luxuriously and happily in Herat Nana, advised her daughter that men will always find fault with women. “ Look at me, Mariam”. Reluctantly, Mariam did. Nana said, “Learn this now and uncover it well, my daughter: Like a compass needle that points north, a mans incriminating finger always finds a woman, Always, you remember that, Mariam”(7). Due to the frustration, regret and harsh treatment of her husband, Nana commits suicide.

After the grave of her mother, Mariam is married to Rasheed when she is 16 years old, and Rasheed is at least twenty-five years older than Mariam. An abusive man who relishes having power over women, Rasheed depicts the worst of men in a patriarchal society. A widowman who lost his only son to drowning, and he hides this truth to Mariam and forces her to bear him another son. Since Miriam’s gets pregnant seven times but loses the babies each time, due to the health complication, she cannot take any baby. She was tortured by him physically and emotionally as Mariam is powerless she cannot think of anything but only a dread, frustration and fear of Rasheed while he enters the home and eventually he seeks to marry a second, much younger wife, Laila.

In Afghanistan, men are allowed to do polygamy with four wives if the husband can treat their wives equally. Gender discrimination starts when the wives are mistreated by their husbands. In the novel, Laila looks more beautiful, Rasheed makes Mariam be the servant of Laila.

He orders his wives to wear the full burqa to keep their honours; Afghan women should wear the burqa. When Laila and Mariam wear the burqa they feel uncomfortable to see, eat and walk. It is massive, and they think hard. The women are the suns that hide behind the wall.

The forced marriage of both Mariam and Laila make them live with the cruel husband whom they do not love. Thus Afghan women have no right to choose their husband. Rasheed continuously torturer Mariam by slapping her, beating her, punching her, and kicking her. He always finds fault with Mariam even though she tries to avoid all her mistake. This clearly shows the gender discrimination and subordination Rasheed criticises Mariam’s cooking. He says that all that Mariam has given him in the marriage is terrible food. Rasheed forced Mariam to chew pebbles as he thinks the rice is not boiled well.

“Get up,” he said. “Come here. Get up.”

He snatched her hand, open-end it, and dropped a handful of pebbles into it.

“Put these in your mouth.”

“What?”

“Put. These. In your mouth.”

“Stop it, Rasheed, I’m___.”

His Powerful hands clasped her jaw. He showed two fingers into her mouth and pried it open, then forced the cold, hard cobbles into it. Mariam seeks against him, mumbling, but he kept pushing the rocks in, his upper lip curled in a smirk.

“Now chew,” he said.

In the mouthful of grit and pebbles, Mariam mumbles a case. Tears were leaking out of the ridges of her eyes.

“CHEW!” he bellowed. A gust of his smoky breath crashed across her face.

Mariam chewed. Something in the back of her mouth broken.

“Good,” Rasheed said. His cheeks were shaking. “Now you know what your rice tastes similar. Now you know what you’ve presented me in this matrimony. Bad food, and zero else. Then he has gone leaving Mariam to spit out pebbles, blood and the fragment of two broken molars. (102-103)

As Laila announced that she is pregnant, Rasheed is ecstatic. He prayed for a boy and held Laila in even higher esteem. They consider the boy baby as their blessing and great pride, but Laila gives birth to a girl baby, named Aziza. Rasheed soon neglects the baby and feels disgusted by the smells and sounds that fill the house. This implies that he knows the baby is not his, and he becomes rude and cruel to Aziza. Rasheed judges to have sex with Laila before six weeks after birth that during which the doctor had warned to abstain, Laila refuses, and Rasheed gets angry and tries to seduce her.

All the women in this novel suffered from great hardship in their lives. In Afghanistan, Women’s value is honoured by their ability to bear boy baby. Laila, due to Rasheed’s cruelty, gives birth to a second child, Zalmai. Rasheed shows treatment to Aziza. He buys toys, and clothes for Zalmai this shows his preference towards boy child by neglecting the girl baby. “I haven’t had a decent night’s sleep in two months,’ Rasheed said. “And the room smells like a sewer. Shit clothes are lying all over the place. I stepped on one just the other night” (230).

The Taliban comes to power, and strict laws are framed for women. The rules are even more severe than Rasheed has been. Taliban beat the women who do not wear burqa and who laugh in public and, all their freedom has been taken away.

Singing is forbidden.

Dancing is forbidden...270.

You will not, under any situations, show your face. You will come with burqa when external. If you do not, you will be rigorously beaten.

Cosmetics are forbidden.

Jewellery is forbidden.

You will not wear charming dresses...271.

Girls are forbidden from frequenting school. All schools for girls will be closed instantly.

Women are forbidden from working.

If you are found criminal of adultery, you will be stoned to death.

Listen. Listen well. Obey. Allah-u-Akbar 271.

All together with Mariam, Laila and her children plan to escape and move to Pakistan. When they try to run away, they are caught by police and returned home. Hence Rasheed tortures them by beating and locking them in various places without food, shelter and light for several days. “Azan rang out a second time, and still Rasheed had not given them any food, and worse, no water. That day, a thick, suffocating heat feel on them. The room turned into a Pressure cooker.” (288). He threatened them if she attempts such an act again, he would kill Mariam first, then Aziza and then he would kill Laila.

The novel “ A Thousand Splendid Suns” tells about the life of women Afghanistan, one of the famous countries in the world. The book tells particularly about the women suppression and the culture that is followed in the country. The novel tells that every human being has a specific limit to bear the pain but Nana, Mariam and Laila being female they cannot be able to take the pain, and they are not even treated as the human being. This novel gains popularity due to its content, which tells about the society which is not written by any of the other writers.

In Afghanistan women are being suppressed in many forms: Women are not allowed to go to school, Women are forced to Marriage, and the feelings of women are not respected and not

even heard of, the girl child is considered as a curse and sons are believed as a blessing. Women are restricted in their way of dressing; Women are oppressed in polygamy. All these cruelties to women are excellently portrayed in A Thousand Splendid Suns.

Work Cited

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